

Development of a Novel Aerospace Component

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Abstract: *The study fabricated a mechanical Special Service Tool (SST) for the extraction of fan hub and impeller of automobile cooling pump system that will help on car's proper maintenance to address over heating of engines. The fabrication started from the metal flat bar with the nut at its middle most part with a rotating threaded bolt constructed and welded to the short metal tube where the bolt holder was inserted. The product was evaluated for standardized hardness and tested in car machine shops. The product has excellent levels on both durability and manageability with very good appearance. The hardness for the flat bar, nut, rotating bolt and holder and short metal tube revealed 394 HBW, 24HRC, 85 HRB, 233 HV 10 and 92 HRB respectively. This gave assurance on the necessary hardness of the product. A significant difference on the speed of extraction of hammering, commercial puller and the SST for both fan hub ($F=79.41$; $p=0.000$) and impeller ($F=346.15$; $p=0.000$) was obtained wherein the SST affirms the fastest extraction time. Thus, the fabricated SST holds confidence for a safer and faster extraction for fan hub and impeller of automobiles' cooling pumps which could help the transportation sector of the country.*

I. Introduction

Automobile Cooling pump is the key part of the automobile cooling system that keep circulate the coolant throughout it and takes away excess heat from engine at different Engine revolution per minute (rpm) and torque conditions (Patel, 2013). But instances of car water pump failures happen internally due to severe corrosion wearing away the impeller blades, or the impeller comes loose on the shaft, or the shaft itself may break from metal fatigue which is caused by flexing due to an out-of-balance fan.

The irregularities on automobile water pump are usually resolved by changing the whole pump by a new one which is very costly (Bacharoudis & Filios, 2008). Meanwhile, opening the water pump by pulling its fan hub is another way to determine the deficient part of the cooling pump.

Since car maintenance is an integral part of owning a vehicle, thus making it inevitable for vehicle owners this study is therefore designed to innovate the quality of work over the traditional way of hammering by developing a Special Service Tool (SST) that pulls the fan hub and impeller of an automobile cooling pump system. The SST can help the automobile owner to easily countercheck the possible failing components inside the cooling pump without breaking the entire pump. This also lowers the probability on automobiles to overheat that causes risk on the lives of the passengers.

The main objective of this study is to invent a Special Service Tool (SST) that can be utilized in extracting both the fan hub and impeller of an automobile cooling pump system. The study aims also to determine the averages of the speed of extractions on using the traditional way of hammering, commercial puller and SST and the significant differences between them.

II. Materials and Methods

Materials and Equipment

The materials that have been used in the study were 10 ½ cm of metal flat bar, threaded bolt, nut, 3 cm and 12 cm of metal tubes/pipes, iron plate, post drill, wrench, screw driver, and welding machine.

General Procedure

In making the *Special Service Tool* (SST), different parts have been prepared/welded and polished first. All components of the SST had integral functions in its application on the automobile's cooling pump.

From the prepared metal flat bar of 14 cm x 8 cm dimension with thickness of 10 mm, a nut has been welded at its middle most part. Moreover, two holes have been drilled side by side of the flat bar for the placement of the

screw supports. These screws exerted the attachment force that obstructed the flat bar for unnecessary movements that were produced by the rotating process that may affect the performance of the extraction (See Fig.1).

Figure 1. Construction of the flat bar bolt receiver

The flat bar served as the flat metal surface which received the threaded bolt where the nut has been located. It pulled the hub and impeller as the threaded bolt has been continuously rotated down to the cooling pump to the shaft. It was imperative that the flat bar was in total rest to avoid unnecessary movements that can be brought by the extraction process, because this could affect the speed of extractions.

Meanwhile, the rotating threaded bolt has been responsible with the exerted force needed to push the middle part of the hub and impeller that caused the pull effect on the metal flat bar to execute the extraction.

In the construction of the rotating threaded bolt, a threaded bolt has been cut in 16.5 cm length and welded to an iron plate that has been molded cylindrically as the pipe. While a short metal tube (3-4 cm in length, maximum) with diameter of 3 cm has been also polished and welded parallel after the molded iron plate. This part served as the hole for the rotator (See Fig.2).

Figure 2. Construction of the Rotating Threaded Bolt

The threaded bolt has been placed perpendicular with the metal flat bar during the time of extraction in the fan hub and impeller.

On the other hand, to an easy rotating process of the rotating threaded bolt, the rotating bolt holder has been also constructed. In the construction of the bolt holder, a metal tubing of diameter 2.5 cm and length of 30 cm has been cut and then polished properly to remove sharp edges (See Fig.3).

Figure 3. Construction of the Rotating Bolt Holder

In assembling the SST, the rotating threaded bolt has been placed exactly forming a 90° angle with respect on the flat bar bolt receiver. The perpendicular position of the threaded bolt on the flat bar was imperative to have the most convenient extraction process on the fan hub and impeller. Angular irregularities on the positioning of the threaded bolt with respect to the flat bar may cause misalignment that could give unsatisfactory performance on the process of extraction.

To complete the assembly of the SST, the rotating bolt holder was inserted to the upper hole of the threaded bolt. This could help the user to have an easy execution of the extraction process (See Fig.4).

Figure 4. Special Service Tool Assembly

Testing of the Product

The efficiency of the designed *Special Service Tool* (SST) was obtained by recording the time spent in extracting the fan hub and impeller of five (5) cooling pumps of different car models that has been conducted with ten (10) trials. The trials have been executed at the different car repair shops in the Municipality of Bongabong, Oriental Mindoro, Philippines. Time started and the time ended have been recorded and tabulated as bases for the total duration of each extraction.

Meanwhile, a survey has been also conducted to 30 respondents who were working on machine shops in Bongabong Oriental Mindoro to determine the level of acceptability of the product in terms of its appearance, durability, and manageability as a *Special Service Tool* (SST) in hub and impeller puller for automobile cooling pumps. The cost effectiveness of the product was also identified.

On the other hand, the average hardness of the SST assembly was tested in the Metals Industry Research and Development Center (MIRDC) – Mechanical Metallurgy Laboratory (MML) in the Department of Science and Technology (DOST) in the Philippines. ASTM E 10-08, ASTM E 18-08b and ASTM 384-11 were applied as Standard Test Methods for Brinell, Rockwell and Vickers Hardness for the metallic samples of the Pumppler assembly such as flat bar bolt receiver, nut (at the middle of the flat bar), rotating threaded bolt, short metal tube and the rotating bolt holder.

III. Results

A. The SST exhibits excellent results for manageability and durability with very good appearance as per evaluation of 30 auto machine shop workers as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Mean responses of 30 machine shopmechanics/workers on the level of acceptability of the designed SST in terms of durability, manageability, and appearance.

Parameter	Mean Response	Description
Manageability	3.9	Excellent
Durability	3.9	Excellent
Appearance	3.4	Very Good

B. The important parts of the SST has the necessary hardness requirements which will be responsible in the smooth application of the tool during actual extraction as depicted in Table 2.

Sample Designation	Test Analysis	Method	Average Hardness
Flat Bar Bolt Receiver	Brinell Hardness	ASTM E10-08	394 HBW
Nut	Rockwell Hardness	ASTM E18-08b	24 HRC
Rotating Threaded Bolt	RockwellHardness	ASTM E18-08b	85 HRB

Short Metal Tube	Rockwell Hardness	ASTM 18-08b	92 HRB
Rotating Bolt Holder	Vickers Hardness	ASTM E384-11	233 HV 10

Table 2. Standardized test results on the hardness of the SST as newly designed Special Service Tool (SST) in terms of its flat bar bolt receiver, nut (at the middle of the flat bar), rotating threaded bolt, short metal tube, and the rotating bolt holder.

C. The fabricated SST exhibits fastest time of extraction for fan hub as compared to the use of the conventional way of hammering and the commercial puller as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Recorded speed of extraction (in minutes) for fan hub of five different car models using the SST, hammering and the commercial puller.

D. The fabricated SST affirms faster time of extraction for impeller as compared to the use of the conventional way of hammering as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Recorded speed of extraction (in minutes) for impeller of five different car models using the SST, and hammering.

IV. Discussion

As can be gleaned on the presented results, an average response of 3.9 was obtained for both manageability and durability which can be described as excellently manageable and durable respectively. This is anchored with the study of Baurer (1981) that the constructions of various types of Special Service Tools hold high confidence when it comes to manageability and durability since the ultimate purpose of designing these tools is to lessen the effort

in doing complicated and difficult tasks particularly on mechanical aspects. It also has a very good appearance (M=3.4) which could lead to a promising marketability.

On the other hand, the SST holds the confidence of a smoother and safer extraction process as it affirms promising results for the hardness of its specific important parts (AMC, 2015; Degout & Farges, 1989; James, 2008; & Hundley, 1987).

In addition, the fabricated SST affirms significant difference to the hammering and commercial puller when it comes to the extraction of fan hub and impeller wherein the SST also exhibited the fastest time as supported by Woo and Christopherson (2002) that even the shaft which is harder to extract from the cooling pump system can be removed easier when a special tool was designed for it. Pullers worked faster on pumps with larger hub (Hundley, 1987).

V. Conclusion

Based on the results and findings of the study, it can be concluded that the SST has the capability to extract both the fan hub and impeller of an automobile's cooling pump system at less time. The designed Special Service Tool (SST) has an excellent durability and manageability that will aptly help mechanics to demonstrate ease and convenience in using the product. From this, the SST is considered as a user friendly tool. Meanwhile, the product had a very good appearance which was also good basis to be considered in the marketability of the SST. On the other hand, the SST assembly assured the necessary hardness needed in the smooth execution of the extraction process on the fan hub and impeller of the automobile cooling pump system. The developed SST affirmed fast speed in the extraction of the fan hub and impeller without breaking or destroying the housing of an automobile's cooling pump. This will resolved the problem on a-must costly purchasing of a new cooling pump system. Through this, car maintenance on its cooling pump will be no longer put aside. It will then lessen the risk of car overheating that could really put the lives of every passenger into danger (Lavacot, 2013). **References**

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